

Integrating IoT and AI Middleware for Enhanced Agricultural Practices

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Abstract— The amount and nature of work in rural areas have changed due to the use of AI devices such as discourse acknowledgment, regular language handling, master frameworks, and machine vision. These changes have been brought about by the growing global population, increased interest in food, climate change, and water availability. Researchers and experts are currently working to incorporate new IoT developments into smart farming to assist ranchers in producing better manures, seeds, and crop assurance through the use of AI technologies. This will help the profitability of ranchers as well as the country's economy as a whole. Three primary domains where artificial intelligence (AI) is starting to emerge are farming robots, predictive analytics, and land and crop monitoring. Ranchers are using sensors and soil tests more frequently in this method for gathering data that the executive frameworks may use for further analysis. This publication demonstrates its dedication to the field by providing an overview of applications of artificial intelligence in the farming industry. An introduction to artificial intelligence (AI) and a study of all AI techniques applied in the agricultural sector are presented at the outset. These techniques include AI, mastering systems, picture handling, PC vision, and the Internet of Things via Universal Middleware. In order to find out how artificial intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT) are used in cultivating, this study includes a thorough review of the literature.

Keywords— Agriculture, The Impact of AI Connectivity of Devices, systematic study of literature

I. INTRODUCTION

Smart farming makes use of information technology to optimize complex agricultural processes. The technology of communication and information is used to improve the agricultural production system. Agriculture is one of the major producing sectors. It is divided within three primary subcategories: hydroponics, supplies as well as ecological services, and domesticated creatures (creativity and being welfare). It is connected to every aspect of the agrarian revolution. Intelligent technology (machine learning) refers to a wide variety of technological uses related to the anticipated advancement of sophisticated personal computers, machines, or sensors that may mimic human actions to carry out tasks for people's benefit and deftly serve society. Application programs handle these tasks through the use of information processing and instruction from technology devices. Accurate cultivation is used by brilliant agribusiness, which combines AI techniques with traditional horticultural procedures, to monitor crop enhancement and boost public markets [1].

We don't find it amazing how technology has affected almost every aspect of our lives. Cooling fans, air conditioning units, coolers, plants, doors, and many more objects are capable of communicating with one another and making judgments based on actual conditions using almost any human piece of information. Machine learning (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT) created an essential dedication across all domains, including wearable's and smart homes, astute metropolitan areas, astute structures like Universal Software, Initiative for Open Service Portals and Innovative Services Framework, vehicles connected to the contemporary the web, store network management, medical care, and so forth [2].

The IoT, or the Internet of Things is a broad category of diverse linked together devices that converse with

one another and execute predefined tasks based on collected sensor data using a variety of protocols and architectural styles. When AI and IoT are combined, things become wiser and rational decisions are made without the need for human intervention [3].

We looked at the information derived from the various devices that we use every day to interact with the modern environment.

AI is crucial in IoT devices when it comes to processing this data [4]. In this decade of unparalleled technological progress, agriculture is no longer an exception. AI and IoT have a big impact on activities related to agriculture as well.

Research indicates that approximately 17% to 18% of India's GDP comes from agriculture [5]. Advanced crop creation relies on a number of internal and external factors that are difficult to predict in advance, such as weather patterns, manure application, soil quality, insect control, crop health, weed management, temperature rise or fall, and so forth.

Conventionally applied methods fall short in producing optimal outcomes, particularly in terms of predicting the behaviour of a produce and the amount of water it will need. When taken in excess, supplements lose value, and when used in insufficient amounts, crop development is disrupted. Approximately 62% of water is wasted during irrigation processes [6].

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the World Wide Web of Things (IoT) assist in the collection, processing, and identification of critical elements that ultimately contribute to agricultural production [7]. The agricultural system takes into account a number of variables, such as temperature, precipitation totals, weed management, water management across the board, crop health monitoring, and weed control.

The Internet of Things and artificial intelligence greatly benefitted every industry, including robotic water distribution structures, agricultural examining data and models evaluation required for and supply, infestation of crops prognosis using image manipulation, and the precise application of insecticides that the help among sensors.

Ranchers' lives have been easier thanks to technology and agribusiness because they no longer have to visit every field at dusk and stay there until the water or electricity is turned on [9]. An rising variety of novel techniques, instruments, and protocols are being used to introduce the concepts of agricultural precision, intelligent agriculture, and digital farming [10].

Generally speaking, the tasks that follow can be completed using various AI applications in agriculture.

- Inspecting the yields and the soil (check the wellness of the crop). AI might be used by organizations to monitor harvests and soil health continuously, estimating agricultural outputs and determining the most profitable time for collection.
- Problem identification (early detection of plant illnesses is beneficial to employ the right plan to combat it). When it comes to the early stages of plant illnesses, ranchers will truly want to implement the greatest disease-fighting techniques.
- A cultivating robot that can handle the challenging tasks. AI models, machines, detectors, vision for machines, and artificial intelligence can all be used to help reps complete retaking assignments more quickly and accurately.
- Educates (points in the appropriate path)
- Anticipating crop output (predicting when to plant). With the use of AI tools and procedures, it is feasible to determine the ideal moment to prepare arenas and plant seeds, improving yield and valuation with precise timing.
- Strategic spraying, which reduces expenses. When smart spraying is employed, the amount of crops lost in the field due to traditional harvesting methods is reduced. One of the most important methods for controlling plant diseases brought on by fungi, bacteria, and pest insects is chemical spraying.

Global population is expected to grow quickly, from 7.8 billion in 2020 to almost 11 billion in the near future, according to estimates from the United Nations. According to the FAO [11], here will be 8.5 billion individuals on the planet by 2025 and 9.6 billion by the end of 2050. In order to feed the world's rapidly expanding population, food must be grown appropriately. Traditional agricultural methods are insufficient to meet the growing demand for agricultural products since ranchers need to increase output in addition to providing consumers with higher-quality food.

It is emphasized that different courses of applications using the Internet of Things, robotization, AI, neural networks, and AI methods should be used effectively to increase the production of nourishment, additionally the quality of the nourishment that is delivered because the global population is growing at a very rapid rate and there is a growing demand for food in tandem with this demand [12]. Figure 1 illustrates the possible applications of AI in cultivation.

Figure 1: Artificial Intelligence and Agriculture

Several searches terms (Table 1) related to the application of AI and the Internet of Things in solving horticulture problems were employed to extract content from peer-reviewed scholarly distributions and conferences in order to obtain data focusing on the key components of this SLR. The information was gathered, among other places, from Google Researcher, Science Direct, and the Agricultural Research Data Collection.

An optimization technique known as "precision farming" combines measurement, analysis, and observation tailored to the field and crop. Precision farming may be governed by two technologies: robots and massive amounts of data & advanced analytics. It is better described by the 4 R's: right time, right place, right quantity, and right way [13]. "Smart farming": describes the process of obtaining information from the field and making astute use of it to execute the planned tasks. It impacts every facet of agricultural operations and makes use of data and digital technologies [14].

Keywords for Findings	Output
AI AND Farming Practices	55
Agriculture AND Machine learning	98
Agriculture AND Internet of Things	52
Smart sensing AND agriculture	85
4.0 Farming	8
a clever farmer	74
Farming with precision	85

Table 1: Use search strings to recover information during exploratory recognizable evidence

II. E-PAGRAM

"Digital farming" is a concept that takes into account both precise and clever farming. The approach values the gathered information and generates decisions that may be carried out at some point in the future. Additionally, it is priceless for users because it provides clients with knowledgebase data [154].

Despite the adoption of some modern tactics, there are still some obstacles that must be resolved to be able to continue developing. The ongoing review article's goal is to examine a few proven systems used in modern farming and highlight the genuine potential of these practices for the future. Figure 2 depicts the architecture of WSN nodes using Universal Middleware.

Figure 2: Universal Controller and WSN node layout

Wide research is still needed in developing fields that are significant enough to noticeably impact large-scale ranches in developed countries as well as small-scale ranches in developing countries [16]. Despite the fact that the application of Internet and the acquisition of precise horticulture can greatly improve ranchers' overall produce and farming methods.

It is important to consider how these developments could be accessible to rural areas and non-industrialized nations, as the adoption of accurate horticulture relies on factors other than the application of these technologies on commercial ranches.

More efficient and dependable computer systems and networks in terms of electrical power supplies, latency in the network, throughput, and performance are required for rural areas. This decreases network latency in places with weaker connection and higher bandwidth constraints, improving access to the benefits of precision agriculture [17]. This will make resources for cyclical farming—which may boost output as well as additional facets of agricultural output—more accessible to burgeoning small-scale farmers.

III. METHODOLOGY FOR SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

Food and agriculture are two of the most significant aspects of human existence on this planet. This industry may benefit from artificial intelligence and related subdomains, such as computer vision and image processing, and artificial intelligence, to handle a variety of difficulties. IoT equipment can be used to assemble important data from raw to assemble regarding Water and agribusiness systems, even though AI strategies can be used during these periods throughout preliminary production (plant yield and

finding water system leaks), formation (disease place and anticipated weather), managing (item evaluation), and movement (storing and analysis of clients)[18].

Before conducting research and making decisions based on the results, creators should understand, analyse, and categorize the most recent examination distributions in their industry.

For the current literature review, we looked for book parts, meeting papers, and diary entries that looked at AI and IoT applications in cultivation. We concentrated on reputable publications listed in IEEE Xplore, Clarivate, and Scopus [19]. The phases in the systematic examination of the literature that was used for this investigation are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: A comprehensive research review's steps

A) THE PROCESS OF DOING A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW INVOLVES THREE STEPS:

- GETTING READY, DOING, AND REPORTING

During the planning phase, the reasons to conduct an analysis of literature in a specific field are considered.

This example introduces a number of innovative applications, such as efficiency, identifying anomalous actions, harvest and animal checking, locating water system spills, and observation. Despite these application domains, the most promising AI approaches—AI, mastering structures, the growing Internet with Things, and picture/video handling—are also being researched [20].

IV. AGRICOLAR SECTOR

The agricultural sector is greatly impacted by smart farming technologies from a number of perspectives. For example, data gathering and observations on moisture, air temperature, moisture in the soil, and solar intensity from large farms will help improve the effectiveness of water use. Consequently, it will have an impact on the yield overall of agriculture. Using cutting-edge agricultural techniques is essential to increasing food production because the world's population is expanding daily. Thus, profitable farming is

the finest way to increase production of food while maintaining a profit margin. For smart agriculture effective implementation of solutions is necessary and should save resources, time, and cash by utilizing inexpensive sensors and IoT platforms. These changes will benefit the agriculture sector in a number of ways.

Many countries promote research and development on smart farming practices to boost the production of sustainable food and boost farmer profits. There was one example of smart farming in action in the agriculture sector. They addressed the difficulties associated with conducting these drives while taking into account the availability of HR, ecological considerations, and fully functional examination offices [22]. The artificial intelligence (AI) component of an IoT-savvy farming framework is shown in Figure 4. Information from the fields is gathered by WiFi robotics and uavs, and Internet of Things (Internet of Things) devices (such as visual, electrolyte in nature, physical dirt, area, and airflow sensors) and sent over the cloud to the artificial intelligence (AI) brilliant cultivating framework. Clever cultivating frameworks use a variety of AI, image dealing with, Computer vision, remotely identifying, and master framework strategies to extract data from unstructured material and help with executive and navigational cultivation. These methods improve the sustainability, efficiency, and quality of farming and supply organizations [23].

Figure 4: AI-powered IoT-enabled smart agriculture system

Presented an Internet of Things (IoT) based "digital agricultural" method to measure agricultural yield. IoT devices collect data from farms to help farmers with crop monitoring and decision-making. Online and smartphone applications are very useful for sharing product details and streamlining the online purchasing experience. Compared a number of AI- and IoT-based agriculture strategies against conventional farming methods [24]. Their findings show the AI-powered agriculture development is more beneficial and successful, and that ranchers who use smart cultivation have higher expectations for daily pleasures and higher Satisfaction Record scores than ranchers who use traditional farming methods [25].

V. FINAL VERDICT

Intelligent agriculture is a idea that entails continuously managing farms with the use of modern technologies like the Internet of Things, robots, and AI-ML to increase the quantity and quality of goods produced while lessening the requirement for ongoing Work by humans.

Given that the world's population is growing rapidly, these advantages will definitely have an impact on the profitability and scope of the economy. To assist ranchers in using artificial intelligence (AI) to create better seeds and crop. Experts in security, manures, and other fields are encouraging the use of recently developed IoT developments in astute agricultural.

This study has also addressed the most recent applications of AI approaches in smart farming, with a focus on the AI methods or algorithms used and the levels of precision reached [27]. The most recent AI approach, associated applications, and achieved accuracy levels were displayed in tables. Researchers that successfully apply AI approaches have observed very encouraging results. This work has provided thorough justifications for the use of AI in intelligent agriculture. In conclusion, the goal of precision and

intelligent agriculture is to advance agriculture civilization, and it appears that widespread adoption of these technologies by farmers is necessary for agriculture to thrive [28].

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Intelligent agriculture is an idea that entails continuously monitoring ranches with the use of modern technologies like the Internet of Things, robots, and AI to increase the quantity and quality of goods produced while lessening the requirement for ongoing human effort [26]. Given the rapid global population growth, these advantages will likely have an impact on the profitability and expansion of the economy. Experts and researchers are pressing for the use of recently released IoT advancements in astute cultivating to assist ranchers in leveraging AI technology to generate superior seeds, crop security, and manures.

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Permission to Publish

Every author has read the work and is aware that it will be published in xxxxxxxx.

Statement of Data Availability

Due to privacy concerns, the database created and/or analyzed for this study is not publicly accessible, but it can be obtained from the author who created it upon request.

Proclamations

The author(s) affirm that this manuscript is their original work and was never submitted to any other publication.

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